

Examining and comparing the effect of compost and vermicompost and chemical fertilizers on the germination of green bean and kidney bean

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Abstract

Composting is a sustainable process that turns organic waste into nutrient-rich fertilizers for agricultural practices. The product, compost, can replace chemical fertilizers, reducing negative environmental impacts. Results from comparing the growth of green beans and kidney beans in different soil conditions showed the efficiency of using compost instead of artificial fertilizers. Although there are limitations to composting, various actions can be taken to promote more composting practices.

1. Introduction

After years of research and application, composting has become a fundamental method that promotes the sustainable use of natural resources. Composting is a process of recycling natural materials into a nutrient-rich product [1] for sustainable agricultural practices while reducing net carbon emissions and combating climate issues. In real-world scenarios, plant growers often prefer chemical fertilizers because they are nutrient-rich and convenient to obtain. However, composts are increasingly being used in agriculture as soil conditioners and fertilizers in recent years [2]. Similar to a study that found the benefits of using compost in sandy soil [3], I investigated the effectiveness of two different composts—cover crop compost and vermicompost—mixed with loamy soil compared to manufactured gardening soil. The aim was to test whether using compost instead of artificial fertilizers would negatively impact the growth rate of plants or even perform as well as gardening soil by improving the loamy soil structure. A seed germination experiment with green beans and kidney beans was set up.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Soil mixture

Four different components and a bottle of gardening fertilizer were prepared for mixing soil in different combinations. The Normal soil (loose soil), Compost, and

Table 1: Naming labels for different combination of soil mixture

Label	Soil Combination
G	Garden soil
N	Normal soil
En	2/3 Earthworm soil + 1/3 Normal soil
EN	1/2 Earthworm soil + 1/2 Normal soil
Cn	2/3 Compost + 1/3 Normal soil
CN	1/2 Compost + 1/2 Normal soil
An	0.06g of fertilizer per milliliter of Normal soil
CE	1/2 Compost + 1/2 Earthworm soil

Earthworm soil (Vermicompost) were collected at Longhua Biotech Innovation Research Institute, Shenzhen University (114°2'22.782" East, 22°46'13.348" North). In total, eight different combinations with three trials each were prepared and labeled each with names as listed in Table 1.

2.2 Seed germination experiment

2.2.1 Preparation of Plant species

Two plants were selected for our experiment, green bean and kidney bean. Packed products of green beans were bought from the market, and samples of kidney beans were collected at Longhua Biotech Innovation Research Institute, Shenzhen University (114°2'22.782" East, 22°46'13.348" North). Green beans have been soaked in water for four hours before being planted in a soil mixture.

2.2.2 Germination experiments

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Figure 1: 10ml centrifuge tube used for green bean plantation

Figure 2: 15ml centrifuge tube used for kidney bean plantation

10 mL centrifuge tube and 15 mL centrifuge tube were selected for planting green bean and kidney bean. The bottom 1 cm of 10 mL centrifuge tubes was removed (cut) for air exchange (Fig. 1). Green beans were each planted in prepared 10 mL centrifuge tubes with different soil conditions as labeled in Table 1. A hole of 8 mm in diameter was created at the bottom of each 15 mL centrifuge tube for air exchange and kidney bean was planted in each modified 15 mL centrifuge (Fig. 2). For green bean samples, each bean was planted at the mark of 10 mL and covered up the bean with soil to the level of the tube mouth; for kidney beans, each bean was planted 1 cm under the tube mouth and covered up with soil.

2.3 Germination Data analysis

Based on the categories of data collected in our experiment, a growth index for comparing the growth of green beans and kidney beans in different soil conditions was formulated. As depicted in Fig. 3, five categories were measured: 1. Leaf Length (Avg.), 2. Stem Length, 3. Stem Width, 4. Root Length, and 5. Number of Leaves. These five measurements were combined to formulate a growth index using the formula: $1.25 * \text{root length} + 1.25 * \text{leaf length (average)} + 1 * \text{number of leaves} + 1.15 * \text{stem width} + 1.2 * \text{stem length}$, which was aligned to a scale

Figure 3: Parts measured for data collection

of 100. The coefficients reflect the importance of each measurement in indicating the growth of plants. Root length and leaf length are the most important factors for absorbing nutrients and sunlight for photosynthesis.

3. Results

3.1 Green bean germination experiment

Figure 4 illustrates the growth comparison of green beans in different soil conditions. All groups have successfully developed and grown into plants. Green beans planted in groups G, Cn, EN, and CE show similar growth in stem length. However, green beans planted in group Cn developed a much better root system compared to the others. Green beans planted in group EN have significantly shorter stem and root lengths (Fig. 4).

Combining the data collected on green beans (Table 2), a growth index diagram (Fig. 5) was constructed to compare the overall growth of green beans in different soil conditions. Three out of eight groups of soil conditions achieved a growth index above 90: group Cn (100), followed by group G (95.96) and group EN (92.89).

3.2 Kidney bean germination experiment

Among the test groups of kidney beans planted in different soil conditions, only Group G and Group Cn developed healthy stems and roots, with no outliers that failed to grow into plants. As depicted in the following images (Fig. 7),

Figure 4: The documentation of root, stem, and leaf development for Green Beans

Figure 5: Growth Index comparison of Green Beans planted in different soil conditions

Groups N, EN, En, and CE have seeds that decayed in the soil (which are the ones missing data and marked "N/A" in the data table 3). The kidney beans planted in Group En soil developed much shorter stems and roots than those in any other group.

Similar to the results presented in our green bean germination experiment, Group Cn performed the best with a growth index of 100, followed by Group G with a growth index of 95.58 (Fig. 8). Group En performed extremely poorly, with only a growth index of 32.22. In the kidney bean germination experiment, the weight of the overall plant at the end of the 7-day period was also measured

Figure 6: Documentation of the growth of Green Bean on day 6

(Fig. 9). The data collected on plant weight confirmed the trend that kidney beans planted in Group G and Group Cn developed the best, with Group Cn leading with an average weight of 1.487 grams per plant, followed by Group G (1.376 g/plant) and Group N (1.336 g/plant) (Fig. 9). However, four out of eighteen samples degraded in the soil, with one in each of the following groups: Group En, Group CE, Group EN, and Group N.

Table 2: Data collected on five measurement of green bean growth

	Trials	stem length	Stem width	Root length	# of leaf	Leaf Length
G	1	11.60	0.20	6.70	2.00	4.00
	2	9.60	0.20	6.70	2.00	4.70
	3	7.00	0.15	4.40	2.00	2.60
	Avg.	9.40	0.18	5.93	2.00	3.77
Cn(2:1)	1	8.80	0.20	7.30	2.00	2.90
	2	7.80	0.20	7.00	2.00	4.20
	3	10.50	0.20	6.80	2.00	4.50
	Avg.	9.03	0.20	7.03	2.00	3.87
N	1	7.00	0.15	6.50	2.00	3.00
	2	7.60	0.20	6.00	2.00	2.50
	3	3.00	0.20	4.50	2.00	0.90
	Avg.	5.87	0.18	5.67	2.00	2.13
EN(1:1)	1	5.30	0.30	7.20	2.00	1.40
	2	10.50	0.25	6.90	2.00	3.90
	3	11.10	0.20	5.50	2.00	3.30
	Avg.	8.97	0.25	6.53	2.00	2.87
CE(1:1)	1	10.10	0.25	6.60	2.00	3.80
	2	6.40	0.28	2.70	2.00	2.40
	3	9.20	0.15	6.80	2.00	4.50
	Avg.	8.57	0.23	5.37	2.00	3.57
CN(1:1)	1	6.40	0.22	6.90	2.00	1.20
	2	8.80	0.20	6.40	2.00	2.70
	3	7.90	0.27	6.20	2.00	3.10
	Avg.	7.70	0.23	6.50	2.00	2.33
En(2:1)	1	4.20	0.30	1.90	2.00	1.00
	2	4.90	0.30	6.00	2.00	1.70
	3	3.60	0.30	5.80	2.00	2.40
	Avg.	4.23	0.30	4.57	2.00	1.70
An(0.05g/10ml)	1	6.50	0.20	6.20	2.00	1.80
	2	3.90	0.30	2.30	2.00	1.50
	3	10.40	0.20	6.10	2.00	2.60
	Avg.	6.93	0.23	4.87	2.00	1.97

4. Discussion

Exploring the efficiency of replacing chemical fertilizers with compost materials was the aim of this experiment. According to the results, it is clear that the green bean and kidney bean plant groups treated with compost have developed significantly, even slightly better than beans planted in gardening soil. To highlight the importance of this study, the effectiveness of compost soil was confirmed.

4.1 Issues with chemical fertilizer

The heavy use of chemicals in agricultural practices has a huge impact on the environment and is often harmful. Chemical fertilizers are frequently used single-use, which can alter the organic composition of the soil and lead to poor conditions for plant development. Continuous use of chemical fertilizers can increase pests and soil crusting, resulting

in decreased organic matter and contributing to the emission of greenhouse gases [4]. Soil acidification can be caused by the large-scale use of chemicals, diminishing phosphate uptake by crops, increasing the concentration of toxic ions in the soil, and inhibiting crop growth [5]. This may lead to a less diverse soil microbial community, with bacteria involved in nitrogen fixation disappearing. As a result, root growth is highly suppressed.

In addition, the use of chemical fertilizers can lead to serious environmental issues, such as the over-nutrition of runoff water, resulting in problems like algal blooms and water pollution in rivers or coastal environments. Nitrogenous components can enter water bodies through various pathways. For example, nitrogen can reach water through the soil after being decomposed by microorganisms. This pollution makes water unsuitable for drinking and can re-

Figure 7: The documentation of root, stem, and leaf development for Kidney Beans

Figure 8: Growth Index comparison of Kidney Beans planted in different soil conditions

Figure 9: Average weight comparison of Kidney Beans planted in different soil conditions

duce aquatic species in certain bodies of water [6]. Excessive nutrient enrichment, especially nitrogen and phosphorus from human activities—including the use of chemical fertilizers—causes water bodies to shift from oligotrophic to mesotrophic, eutrophic, and ultimately hypertrophic states. The mesotrophic and eutrophic phases exhibit moderate to high nutrient levels, leading to worsening water quality issues. Eutrophication limits water availability for fishing, recreation, industry, and drinking due to increased growth of harmful algae and aquatic plants, as well as oxygen depletion resulting from their decay. This can lead to harmful cyanobacterial blooms in drinking water sources, posing significant health risks to both humans and animals [7].

4.2 The opportunities for using composts

Composting, a strategy for turning organic waste into nutrient-rich materials for agricultural practices, has great advantages compared to the use of chemical fertilizers. Through the use of compost, we can achieve real organic farming, reduce air pollution, promote healthy root development, and increase carbon sequestration. Since compost is a truly organic product, it causes a much less negative impact on soil and water conditions in the surrounding area. Moreover, compared to chemical fertilizers, compost can improve soil structure when applied, providing more space for air exchange and plant development. This could be a big step forward in finding a solution that reduces the use of chemical fertilizers. However, the process of producing compost is complex. Materials, which include green and brown materials, need to be cut into small pieces to react ef-

Table 3: Data collected on five measurement of Kidney Bean growth

		stem length	Stem width	Root length	# of leaf	Leaf Length
G	1	10.2	0.21	7.3	2	1.5
	2	11.8	0.22	7.9	2	1.5
	3	9.4	0.25	9.9	2	0.9
	Avg.	10.47	0.23	8.37	2.00	1.30
Cn(2:1)	1	9.8	0.4	5.1	2	1.8
	2	12.4	0.32	10.3	2	2.2
	3	9.9	0.3	8.8	2	2.25
	Avg.	10.70	0.34	8.07	2.00	2.08
N	1	6	0.3	5.4	0	
	2	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
	3	4.3	0.3	6.8	0	
	Avg.	5.15	0.30	6.10	0.00	0.00
EN(1:1)	1	6.1	0.3	7.5	0	
	2	5.6	0.28	7	2	1.3
	3	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Avg.	5.85	0.29	7.25	1	0.65
CE(1:1)	1	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
	2	10.3	0.3	6.8	2	1.5
	3 (W)	3.2	0.3	4.1	0	
	Avg.	6.75	0.30	5.45	1.00	0.75
CN(1:1)	1	6.3	0.4	9.8	0	
	2	5.4	0.35	3.9	0	
	3	6.3	0.31	9.8	0	
	Avg.	6.00	0.35	7.83	0.00	0.00
En(2:1)	1	5	0.25	6.6	0	
	2	2.7	0.2	1.1	0	
	3	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A
	Avg.	3.85	0.23	3.85	0.00	0.00
An(0.075g/15ml)	1	0	0.29	7.7	2	1.2
	2	4.1	0.35	7	0	
	3	3.3	0.33	9.6	0	
	Avg.	2.47	0.32	8.10	0.67	0.40

fectively in the composting pile. This time-consuming process presents a significant limitation for the spread of composting practices. Tracking humidity and temperature is necessary to ensure smooth progress. Because of the complexity of composting, promoting this practice on a large scale is not easy.

Past studies have pointed out that there are great opportunities in composting. For example, earthworm-processed pig manure has been shown to be efficient in replacing chemical fertilizers in the germination, growth, and yield of tomatoes [8]. Depending on specific settings, different plans should be considered to promote the practice of composting. The most easily obtained materials should be used to set up composting piles in different situations. All these efforts would help contribute to a sustainable solution beyond the sole use of chemical fertilizers.

5. Conclusion

The effectiveness of using compost in plantation practices has been tested in this experiment. Based on the results from the green bean and kidney bean germination experiments, it was demonstrated that the mixture of 2/3 compost and 1/3 normal soil performs better than gardening soil and soil with chemical fertilizers. The data collected in this experiment suggest that compost is effective in replacing chemical fertilizers in regular plantation practices. Continuing with this application, a composting pile has been set up at Basis International School-Park Lane Harbour, aimed at turning organic waste from around the campus into a nutrient-rich product for school gardening maintenance. All these efforts will have a significant positive impact on controlling net carbon emissions and helping fight global environmental issues.

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